

CERTIFICATE OF APPRECIATION

THIS CERTIFIES THAT
TAFAKKUR MANZILI
JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Dilorom Abduazimova

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE LARGE CHOIR IN THE CONCERT PROGRAM OF

SONGS AND DANCE ENSEMBLES

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

2023/MAY

